

Minutes EB23-03
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
29 May 2023 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barney Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apology

Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Upcoming conferences: BISMIS and TDWG (see below)

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New action items from previous meeting

1. FV to send out a poll to determine the date of the next meeting.

Completed

2. FV to circulate the minutes to the EB for their comments within a set time period.

Completed

3. MC to arrange for the posting of the minutes on the ISME webpage.

Completed

4. IS and FV to investigate archiving the minutes on Zenodo.

Ongoing

5. MC and FV to alert the broader community of the posting of the minutes via email, twitter and slack.

Information shared on Twitter, emails to be sent. LMR to share membership list with FV.

6. LMR to investigate hosting of rocket.chat on Innsbruck server.

Ongoing, waiting for IT specialist to return to work.

7. KK to share the names and short CVs of the proposed co-opted members of his working group with FV.

Names and CVs were shared.

8. FV to send out a ballot to the EB to vote for approval of co-opted members of the standards working group.

Ballot was sent to EB members. All five proposed members approved by EB. The Co-opted members are:

Donovan Parks (Microba, Australia)

Ramon Rossello-Mora (IMEDEA; CSIC-UIB, Mallorca, Spain)

Robert Finn (European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), UK)

Alice McHardy (Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany)

Nikos Kyrpides (DOE Joint Genome Institute, LBNL, Berkeley, USA)

9. LMR to provide a proposal on how best to spend the ISME funding for the development of the Registry. LMR to develop a brief to communicate the funding for a prize (grant) to the person or group with the best proposal to further develop the registry.

LMR working on the development of the grant/ prize for the development of the Registry

The EB approved the appointment of a South African student who will assist LMR with work on the registry, including addressing the possible inclusion of effective names in the registry for type species with genomes conforming to the current quality standards. [Redacted]

10. MC to prepare a letter to the Editors of relevant journals on how they can obtain relevant information related to the registration of names prior to publication.

MC and Marike Palmer are currently working on a draft letter. The letter and list of potential journals to be targeted will be shared with the EB as soon as it is completed.

11. KK, BW and ALR to meet with Brian Hedlund and Alison Murray to follow-up on the NFS' RCN and ICB funding on 10 April.

Meeting held and potential strategies were discussed.

12. ALR to create 2 slides for general use to promote the use of the SeqCode.

Four slides were created. It is currently available on the shared drive. [Redacted]

Feedback on ongoing action items

1. MC to have news items posted on the ISME website after consultation with the EB.

Completed

2. EB to decide on person responsible for the newsletter.

EB decided not to produce a newsletter at this point in time.

3. LMR to investigate the EU COST Action funding.

LMR shared the requirements for a Cost Action Proposal. The primary focus will be on networking but there can be inclusion of some running costs. At least 7 partners are required of which at least half should be from COST Inclusiveness Target Countries. LMR requested the EB members with contacts in such countries should please share this information with him.

COST Inclusiveness Target Countries are as follows:

EU Member States	EU Member States Outermost Regions ³	Full Members that are not EU Member States
Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia	French Guiana, Guadeloupe, Martinique, Mayotte, Reunion Island and Saint-Martin (France), Azores and Madeira (Portugal), and the Canary Islands (Spain)	Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Georgia, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Turkey, Ukraine

4. FW to look for Chinese funding opportunities.

FW has requested the assistance of some EB members to work on possible funding from China. KK and LMR will assist.

5. BW and ALR will write a piece for ASM's Microcosm newsletter.

BW contacted the Editor of the ASM Blog. The editor will assist with the writing of the text.

6. [Redacted]

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

This commission will have its first meeting when proposals to amend the SeqCode are received. It is expected that the first meeting will be held during the second half of the year.

Standards Working Group

The membership of the Standards working group has been finalized and a meeting will be held in the near future. KK requested EB members to alert him of any issues that need to be discussed. The issue of genomes with a large number of contigs has been raised. There will also be interactions with the Genome Standards Consortium.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

The working group has had regular meetings. The minutes of the meetings will be stored on the shared drive for internal reference. Currently 40 new names have been validated by the SeqCode.

Reconciliation Commission

MC reported that the main item discussed at their meeting was the possible validation of a name linked to a poor-quality genome to ensure the stability of the names of the higher-ranking taxa linked to this genus. Once a proposal has been finalised it will be discussed by the EB before it is opened for discussion by the SeqCode Community.

5. Amendments of SeqCode regarding *Candidatus* names and orthography

BW reported that a small group is currently looking at suggestions to amend the SeqCode to address issues such as genus names linked to *Candidatus* taxa of higher rank, and how the SeqCode should deal with names that require orthographic corrections.

6. Funding of the Registry

KK to investigate possible RCN funding in collaboration with the other USA partners.

7. Information sharing

KK and FV reported that the target date for articles to be published in the special SeqCode issue of Systematic and Applied Microbiology will be the end of the year.

MC alerted EB members of two upcoming meetings where the SeqCode could be promoted: Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) in Hobart, Tasmania, Australia from 9 – 13 October 2023. (<https://www.tdwg.org/conferences/2023/>)

5th BISMIS meeting, Guangzhou, China from 5 – 8 November 2023. (<https://www.bismis2023.com/>)

The meeting was adjourned.

New action items

1. FV to send out a poll to determine the date of the next meeting.
2. FV to circulate the minutes to the EB for their comments within a set time period.
3. MC to arrange for the posting of the minutes on the ISME webpage.
4. LMR to develop a brief to communicate the funding for a prize (grant) to the person or group with the best proposal to further develop the registry.

5. MC to circulate the letter to the Editors of relevant journals on how they can obtain relevant information related to the registration of names prior to publication.
6. EB members should provide LMR with the details of possible contacts in COST Inclusiveness Target Countries.
7. BW to liaise with the Editor of the ASM Blog on an article to promote the SeqCode.
8. KK and LMR to assist FW with applications for funding from China.
9. EB members should alert KK of any issues that need to be discussed by the Standards working group.
10. KK to investigate possible RCN funding

Ongoing action items

1. EB to prepare a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode for submission to ISME communications after January 2024.
2. IS and FV to investigate archiving the minutes on Zenodo.
3. FV to share the EB minutes via email
4. LMR to investigate hosting of rocket.chat on Innsbruck server.

Minutes prepared by FV, May 29, 2023

Approved 5 June, 2023